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Самарканд, Узбекистан**КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА БОЛЬНЫХ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА, ПЕРЕВЕДЕННЫХ НА САНАТОРНО-КУРОРТНЫЙ ЭТАП РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ****For citation:** A.A. Qilichev, J.A. Rizayev Clinical features of patients transferred to the sanatorium stage of rehabilitation. Journal of cardiorespiratory research. 2023, vol 4, issue 4, pp.43-46 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10572419>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В исследование включено 354 пациента с ишемической болезнью сердца (ИБС), из них 290 мужчин (81,9%) и 64 женщины (18,1%). В январе-декабре 2020 года 331 из этих пациентов была проведена плановая трансплантация коронарных артерий (АКШ). Для сравнения результатов научных исследований мы обследовали 23 пациента с различными формами ишемической болезни сердца, которым не проводилось шунтирование коронарных артерий, а проводилось консервативное лечение. В зависимости от тяжести ишемической болезни сердца и особенностей течения заболевания первоначально проводились консервативные лечебные мероприятия. Благодаря применению кардиохирургического вмешательства у некоторых пациентов удалось улучшить качество жизни.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, шунтирование коронарных артерий, ишемическая болезнь сердца, реабилитация

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The study included 354 patients with coronary heart disease (CHD), including 290 men (81.9%) and 64 women (18.1%). Between January and December 2020, 331 of these patients underwent planned coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). To compare the results of these scientific studies, we examined 23 patients with various forms of CHD who did not undergo coronary artery bypass grafting but were conservatively treated. Depending on the severity of coronary heart disease and the specifics of the disease course, conservative therapeutic measures were initially taken. Due to the application of cardiosurgical intervention, some patients managed to improve their quality of life.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, coronary artery bypass grafting, coronary heart disease, rehabilitation

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Tadqiqotga koronar arteriya kasalligi (YuIK) bilan og'rigan 354 bemor kiritilgan, ulardan 290 nafari erkaklar (81,9%) va 64 nafari ayollar (18,1%). 2020 yil yanvar-dekabr oylarida ushbu bemorlarning 331 nafari koronar arteriya transplantatsiyasini (AKSh) amalga oshirdi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijalarini taqqoslash uchun biz koronar arteriya shuntlash operatsiyasini o'tkazmagan, ammo konservativ davolash bilan davolangan koronar arteriya kasalligining turli shakllari bo'lgan 23 bemorni tekshirdik. Yurak ishemik kasalligining og'irligiga va kasallikning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga qarab, dastlab konservativ davolash choralari o'tkazildi. Kardiojarrohlik aralashuvidan foydalanish tufayli ba'zi bemorlar hayot sifatini yaxshilashga muvaffaq bo'lishdi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, koronar arteriya bypass grefti, koronar arteriya kasalligi, reabilitatsiya

Many authors note that in the complex treatment of CHD patients, physical, climatic, and psychotherapeutic factors play important roles as nonmedicamentous factors of influence. The use of combinations of medication and nonmedication methods provides greater effectiveness of therapy at lower doses, which reduces the risk of adverse reactions [4; 5].

Relevance.

The most widespread cardiovascular disease is coronary heart disease. CHD plays a dominant role in mortality from circulatory system diseases (46,8%). Every year the mankind loses approximately 3 million inhabitants; more than one third of them are persons of working age.

However, the potential of CABG to improve the quality of life and prognosis of patients manifests itself in the postoperative period [3, 4, 14]. Available data show that despite the increase in the number of ACL operations performed and objective improvement in the condition of the majority of surgical patients (85.6%), only 40-48.6% of all patients returned to labour without a reduction in the preoperative level of working capacity and qualifications [6, 8, 10].

Currently, medical rehabilitation is defined as "a set of medical and psychological measures aimed at full or partial restoration (or compensation) of disturbed or lost functions of the affected organ or system of the body, as well as maintaining the recovery of body functions after the completion of acute onset or exacerbation of chronic pathological process in the body". [1, 2, 10]. Medical rehabilitation care, including primary, sanitary and high-tech medicine, is routinely provided as part of specialized medical care [5, 9, 13].

The emergence and development of cardiological rehabilitation as a branch of cardiology was associated with the development of systems for restorative treatment of patients after myocardial infarction (MI) in the 1960s. Using the example of rehabilitating patients with acute MI, methods of rehabilitating cardiological patients, including after myocardial revascularisation procedures, were scientifically substantiated and validated.

The combination of optimal drug therapy and myocardial revascularization, in particular coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG), is considered the most promising treatment for severe, rapidly progressive drug-resistant CHD and has the greatest contribution to disability and mortality.

The main components of rehabilitation interventions are appropriate pharmacotherapy, physical and psychological rehabilitation, education and dynamic follow-up. The high clinical efficacy of each of the rehabilitation interventions is considered to be absolutely proven.

Study Materials and Methods.

Out of 354 patients with cardiovascular disease, the study included people aged 36 to 69 years, of whom 290 were male (81.9%) and 64 female (18.1%). Planned ACS treatment was provided to 331 patients aged 57.7 to 7.8 years between January and December 2020. For comparison, 23 patients with myocardial infarction (MI) who received conservative treatment and did not receive surgical revascularization for various reasons were studied.

During the rehabilitation stage, dynamic examination is carried out:

- at the hospital stage - 354 patients admitted to the cardiology departments of the rehabilitation centre between 2018 and 2020;
- at the sanatorium stage - 125 patients who underwent rehabilitation in a sanatorium, including 95 who underwent rehabilitation at the late hospital stage;
- at the outpatient and polyclinic stage - 86 patients.

The majority of patients (291 patients, or 82.2%) suffered from angina pectoris III and IV FC at the time of surgery. A total of 36.2% of patients (128 people) received regular medical care. The average

frequency of visits to a cardiologist was 4.1 plus or minus 1.7 (from 1 to 8). Preparation of necessary documents and preoperative examination were the main goals of the majority (55.1%) of all referrals to a physician; these procedures occurred 3 to 6 months before hospitalization in the hospital.

In 245 patients (69.2%), the total CHOL level was determined at least once from the onset of CHD before surgery (including the period of preoperative examination).

The total CHOL concentration was less than 4.5 mmol/L in 58 (16.4%) patients; in 62 (17.5%) patients, it was between 4.5 and 5.2 mmol/L; in 126 (35.6%) patients, it was between 5.2 and 6.5 mmol/L; and in 108 (30.5%) patients, it exceeded 6.5 mmol/L.

LDL levels were above 3.0 mmol/l in 53.7% (190 patients) and 64.7% (229 patients) of the patients. LDL levels were above 4 mmol/l in 28.5% (101 patients) and above 5 mmol/l in 13.0% (46 patients). A hypertriglyceridaemia level above 1.7 mmol/l was recorded in 44.9% of the patients (159 patients).

Results.

The patient is given an individualized exercise plan and advice on how to take care of themselves after completing treatment in the hospital. They are then sent to the rehabilitation unit at a neighbouring sanatorium to continue their treatment.

Patients who have undergone CABG surgery cannot be referred to a sanatorium for postoperative rehabilitation if they have the following contraindications:

coronary circulatory insufficiency accompanied by frequent attacks of angina pectoris and low exercise tolerance (less than 50 W);

Characteristic cardiac rhythm disturbances included paroxysmal supraventricular or ventricular tachycardia; frequent, polytopic, group or early (S on T) extrasystole; atrioventricular block of II-III degree; and marked bradycardia.

evidence of recently detected focal myocardial changes confirmed by laboratory electrocardiogram data; stage III: hypertension with internal organ damage that was not treated with hypotensive drugs;

presence of other diseases causing fever;

persistent thromboembolic phenomena, especially in the cerebral vessels, which interfere with limb movement; presence of a wound surface in the area of the postoperative suture, which requires regular dressings;

Severe concomitant diseases of internal organs that require special treatment approaches;

malignant tumours; infectious diseases.

The effectiveness of the sanatorium stage was evaluated in 125 patients with CHD who underwent CABG.

A total of 125 patients with CHD were admitted to the sanatorium stage of rehabilitation 30-40 (38.3±3.7) days after CABG (main group). The comparison group consisted of 18 patients who did not undergo sanatorium rehabilitation.

Treatment of patients in both groups included a regimen, diet according to Table 10, therapeutic gymnastics, dosed walking, magnetolaser therapy for postoperative scars, dry-air carbon dioxide baths and drug therapy as indicated. The therapeutic complex of the patients in the main group also included IBT in the mode of interdaily atmospheric pressure fluctuations. Training was carried out every day. The duration of the procedure was thirty minutes, and the whole course of treatment included ten to twelve procedures.

The results showed that exercise tolerance improved in both groups of patients after CABG (Table 1).

The threshold power of load (W), the volume of work performed (A) and the "double product" (DP) increased significantly. Nevertheless, when comparing quantitative indicators of

haemodynamic support of the circulatory system, these changes were more noticeable in the group of patients who received IBT. Threshold power, the volume of work performed and "double product" use were

obviously greater in this group. The chronotropic (IChHR) and inotropic (IIHR) heart reserve indices indicate increased physical performance and ability to adapt.

Table 1
Effect of sanatorium rehabilitation on physical performance and central hemodynamics (M±m)

Indicators	Main group (n=125)	Comparison group (n=18)
W,W	105,5±3,6	95,5±2,7 **
A, kgm/min	3557,8±130,6	3190,6±131,7 *
DP, stand.unit	250,8±5,5	231,2±6,4 **
IChHR, stand.unit	75,4±2,6	66,3±2,3 **
IIHR, stand.unit.	53,9±1,7	48,5±1,8 *
CEI, stand.unit.	1,9±0,06	2,2±0,08 **
PAC, stand.unit.	73,4±1,7	64,5±1,8**
EF,%	52,8±1,5	49,7±1,8 **
ES, ml	67,5±4,1	68,1±1,6*
ED, ml	132,0±5,6	136,9±5,3

* - reliability of differences, $p < 0.05$; ** -significance of differences, $p < 0.01$.

In addition, the cost-effectiveness index (CEI), which measures the conditional cost of the heart per unit of work produced, shows that sanatorium rehabilitation saves more money on the functioning of the circulatory system. This ratio shows that the load performed by the patients in the main group requires less muscular work, which indicates the effectiveness of the applied method of treatment.

Changes in the physical adaptation coefficient (PAC), which was significantly greater in the main group, are evidence of the therapeutic effect of sanatorium rehabilitation.

In our study, we used echocardiography data to assess various hemodynamic parameters. After undergoing a course of sanatorium rehabilitation, a significant increase in ejection fraction (EF) was found, as was a trend toward a decrease in end-systolic (ES) and end-diastolic (ED) heart volumes, respectively, with a reliability of $P < 0.05$.

At admission to the sanatorium stage of rehabilitation in patients with CHD after CABG, a significant decrease in central hemodynamics

and physical performance is observed. The application of a complex programme of medical rehabilitation improves the clinical and functional states of patients and significantly improves quality of life.

Conclusions.

Patients who passed the 2nd stage of sanatorium rehabilitation and demonstrated high rehabilitation potential were referred to the outpatient and polyclinic stage with recommendations to follow a hypolipidemic diet if they demonstrated the following characteristics: tolerance to a physical load of 100 W or more, management of complications during the early postoperative period, an ejection fraction of 50% or more, normalization of psychological status, and high motivation to return to work. Patients who failed to eliminate early postoperative complications were referred to the outpatient and polyclinic stage with recommendations to follow a hypolipidemic diet.

Thus, the implementation of the main directions for the improvement of medical and social rehabilitation will contribute to the reduction of disability among patients with CHD, improvement of quality of life after CABG, and return to society.

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